

AWARENESS AND RISK FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH ORAL CANCER
IN GENERAL PUBLIC OF LAHORE

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Abstract

Background: The high incidence of oral cancer in Asian countries is attributed mainly to smoking habits and the use of smokeless tobacco, which is very common in Pakistan. It is a significant global health concern, as cancer can develop inside the mouth, affecting the lips, gums, tongue and lining of the cheek. A timely recognition of signs in general population can aid to curb the advancement of disease by early detection which is only possible if the community is well aware with the knowledge of risk factors associated with oral cancer.

Objective: This survey-based study was adopted to gauge the level knowledge and necessary awareness required regarding oral cancer in the general population of Lahore.

Materials and Methods: For the purpose of this study, a self-administered questionnaire was employed using cross-sectional survey-based design and participants were selected using convenience sampling method in Lahore. A total of 398 people participated in this study; the collected data were analyzed via descriptive statistics.

Results: Only 56.8% of the participants were familiar with oral cancer. The participants identified “smoking” and use of “smokeless tobacco” as the major risk factors that contributed to oral cancer such that 95.6% participants acknowledged the risk due to smoking and 70.9% of the participants acknowledged the potential risk due to smokeless tobacco use. It was quite concerning that just 67.4% of the participants successfully identified red lesions, while only 38.8% recognized white lesions as early signs of oral cancer.

Conclusions: The results indicate that the extent of knowledge concerning oral cancer in the subject population is not up to the mark. Hence, implementing educational and awareness programs such as seminars and workshops should be held to increase the awareness of public population in Lahore.

INTRODUCTION

In accordance with World Health Organization (WHO) statistics, oral cancer is ranked among the three most prevalent cancers in South Asian regions and is the 15th deadliest reason of death globally [1]. Tobacco and alcohol consumption are the most critical risk factors for oral cancer [2]. The prevalence of oral cancer in Southeast Asia and African countries is due to the habits of the public in these regions, which include smoking, high levels of alcohol consumption and the ability to chew tobacco; this incident risk is greater in males than in females [3]. Two to four% of the cancers diagnosed in the United States are oral cancer, of which only 50% have lived for 5 years. The occurrence of oral cancer is remarkably high in Sri Lanka, with 40% prevalence and 50% prevalence in India, compared with its incidence in Western countries, where oral cancer accounts for 2-4% of cases. Compared with other types of cancers, in the past 16 years, there has been no success in increasing the survival rate of patients suffering from cancer. The incidence of oral cancer in males is twice that in females. Second, it is prevalent in individuals aged 40-60 years [4, 5].

Typically, this cancer is known to develop in patients over 40 years of age, with a predominance in males. However, some epidemiological studies have also concluded that it may affect young females even with no history of smoking or other risk factors [6]. Oral cancer can be prevented by shunning lifestyle and habits to cause cancer and by performing a regular mouth examination [7].

One of the main contributing risk factors to oral cancer is lifestyle, as people develop habits that are contrary to their health and well-being [8]. Tobacco smoke is identified as having approximately 60 cancer-causing agents, while the smokeless form of tobacco constitutes approximately 16 carcinogens. High oral consumption of alcohol contributes to approximately 7-19% of cases of subject cancer, and the hazard of oral cancer in drinkers is 2-3 times higher than that in nondrinkers. Both tobacco and alcohol have psych activity and affect the brain in such a way that the body craves

increased intake, leading to addiction [9]. Individuals who habitually consume both tobacco and alcohol at the same time are at increased threat for likelihood of oral cancer [10]. The risk increases with increasing age, as geriatrics are dependent on caretakers for oral health and hygiene and are immunocompromised [11]. Five million deaths per year are caused by tobacco, and the world comprises approximately 1 billion smokers. The rate of death is expected to exceed 10 million in the near future, so an approach to minimize smoking is a global concern [12].

Approximately 90% of oral cancer cases are mainly attributed to oral squamous cell carcinoma, with the survival rate of five (05) years [13]. Common sites where it manifests itself are the tongue and floor of the mouth and account for 50% of cases, whereas other sites of manifestation are the buccal mucosa, gingiva, soft palate, retromolar areas and often the hard palate and the back of the tongue [14]. The symptoms with which the disease manifests itself are as follows: 30-40% of complaints are pain, which usually piques the formation of distinctly sized lesions and may progress to severe symptoms along with difficulty in speech, ulceration and inflammation at the affected site [15]. Lesions vary in size from a few millimeters to centimeters, whereas at the initial stage of disease, these lesions are so small that they are asymptomatic [16]. Early diagnosis of oral cancer at the initial stages reduces the likelihood of surgery and increases the survival rate. Confirmation of the diagnosis is performed with the help of biopsy [17].

Prevention of oral cancer can strongly reduce its prevalence; thus, an understanding and awareness of disease in the community are highly essential for a better cure and prognosis. The study under discussion was employed in order to evaluate the general public of Pakistan for the knowledge as well as awareness of oral cancer and to assess the prevalence of smoking in the community.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN: This was a cross-sectional observational study performed on the general public of Lahore via a self-administered questionnaire. The ethical committee of University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences Lahore approved the study with IRB NO 180/IRC/BMR.

TOOL: A self-administered questionnaire with close-ended questions was used to assess the awareness level of the public. The questionnaire consisted of five parts including demographics; awareness of oral cancer; signs and symptoms; factors associated with risk; and sources of information. The demographics included information on the respondent's age, sex, education level, marital status and identification of smoking habits. The respondents were asked about their age, alcohol consumption, sunlight exposure, smokeless tobacco use and smoking in terms of risk factors. The respondents were asked about their signs and symptoms, and their responses concerning a specific symptom were recorded as "yes", "no" or "don't know".

PROCEDURE: A pilot study was conducted with over 50 subjects and later an active face-to-face interview technique employing a validated questionnaire in the general population of Lahore, Pakistan. A total of 398 people participated in this survey and were selected from various universities, schools, shops and hospitals in Lahore. Participant consent was obtained before data collection. After each interview, each participant was individually informed and educated about the actual factors attributing to oral cancer as well as its signs and symptoms.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS: After compilation of the data, the data were analyzed via differential statistics.

RESULTS

A total of 398 people participated in this study. The demographics of the participants can be seen

in Table 1. The sample included 69.1% males and 30.9% females. The ages of the participants were such that 4.8% of the participants were younger than 18 years. In the Matriculation, 52.3% of the participants were aged 18-24 years, 21.6% were aged 25-39 years, 17.3% were aged between the range of 40-59 years, and 4% were on advance age of 60 years and above. None of the female participants smoked; however, 29% of the male participants were smokers. These findings are presented in Table 1. About 56.8% of the participants had heard about the cancer. Among those who knew about it, 43.2% learned from public media, 36.1% learned from friends and family, 6.6% from dentists and 4% from physicians.

Approximately two-thirds (74.9%) of the participants believed oral cancer to be preventable. Many misconceptions about oral cancer were present, with 41% of participants believing it was contagious. When it came to risk factors, 95.6% identified smoking and 70.9% recognized smokeless tobacco use as major contributors to oral cancer. Alcohol consumption was identified as one of the key factors associated with risk of oral cancer by 66.5% of the respondents. However, only 35.2% and 38.8% of the participants attributed advance age and exposure to the sun as risk factors accompanying oral cancer. The knowledge and understanding of the respondents regarding initial signs and symptoms of oral cancer was that 80.6% correctly identified non-healing ulcers, and 67.4% and only 38.8% respondents accurately acknowledged the appearance of red and white patches among initial markers of oral cancer. The formation of lumps and swelling was identified by 67.4% of the participants. Table 3 shows an association, i.e., p value < 0.05 , between education and awareness as significant in terms of whether the participants had ever heard of oral cancer.

Table 1. Demographics of participants & smoking status

Gender:	Frequency	Marital Status:	Frequency
Male	275 (69.1%)	Single	253 (63.6%)
Female	123 (30.9%)	Married	145 (36.4%)
Age			
Range	No. of participants	Frequencies	
Below 18	19	4.8	
18-24	208	52.3	
25-39	86	21.6	
40-59	69	6.3	
60 and above	16	16	
Total	398	100%	
Education level:		Smoking status:	
Primary or below	83 (20.9%)	Smokers	117 (29.8%)
Matriculation	47 (11.8%)		
Intermediate	26 (6.5%)		
Under graduation	178 (44.7%)	Nonsmokers	281 (70.6%)
Graduation	42 (10.6%)		
Post-graduation	22 (5.5%)		

Figure 1: Age of the participants

Figure 2. Level of Education of the participants

Table 2: Knowledge of Participants regarding Oral Cancer

VARIABLE	YES	NO	DON'T KNOW
General Knowledge			
Heard of oral cancer	226 (56.8%)	172 (43.2%)	
Oral cancer is preventable	170 (74.9%)	20 (8.8%)	37 (16.3%)
Oral cancer can be treated	141 (62.1%)	41 (18.1%)	45 (19.8%)
Oral cancer is contagious	93 (41%)	74 (32.6%)	60 (26.4%)
Risk factors for oral cancer			
Old age	80 (35.2%)	93 (41%)	54 (23.8%)
Smoking	217 (95.6%)	6 (2.6%)	4 (1.8%)
Smokeless tobacco use	161 (70.9%)	31 (13.7%)	35 (15.4%)
Alcohol drinking	151 (66.5%)	40 (17.6%)	36 (15.9%)
Exposure to sun	88 (38.8%)	76 (33.5%)	63 (27.8%)
Sign of Oral cancer			
Non healing ulcer	183 (80.6%)	17 (7.5%)	27 (11.9%)
Red patches	153 (67.4%)	14 (6.2%)	60 (26.4%)
White patches	88 (38.8%)	50 (22%)	59 (39.9%)
Lump	153 (67.4%)	15 (6.6%)	59 (26%)

Figure 3. Source of information for oral cancer

Table 3: Cross tab between education and having you ever heard of oral cancer?

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	163.554 ^a	30	.000
Likelihood Ratio	106.423	30	.000
N of Valid Cases	398		

DISCUSSION

It is crucial and pertinent to note that for promoting earlier clinical identification and presentation of oral cancer, the community must be made aware about oral cancer and its associated signs and symptoms, contributing factors and menace of smoking. By educating the community about these early indicators, patients are more likely to seek timely medical attention, ultimately improving survival rates. However, there is a notable lack of data regarding the extent of understanding about oral cancer among the public in Lahore, which poses significant challenges for the development of effective community and national health policies aimed at increasing patient survival and quality of life. Consequently, this study aims to assess the knowledge, understanding as well as awareness of oral cancer in community of Lahore.

In 2022, a research survey was conducted at 3 university hospitals in Poland and Germany. 465

adults highlighted that 65.4% of the subjects had prior knowledge about oral cancer, mainly through the internet and mass media. Alarmingly, only 20% of the participants had undergone physical examination [18]. The findings of our study are supported by the findings of a similar study conducted in Yemen, such that, at the conclusion of this study it was brought to light that population of Lahore lacked the knowledge regarding the subject disease; it was quite concerning that merely 56.8% of respondents knew about oral cancer. Similarly, compared with study conducted in Yemen, 71.5% respondents were familiar with the term oral cancer. This is a high alert for health functionaries as the results call for the urgent need of implementing intense public awareness and educational programs in order to enhance the awareness of public regarding do's and don'ts of factors associated with oral cancer [19].

A similar study was conducted in Saudi Arabia to evaluate the understanding as well as awareness of the general public, where merely 53.6% respondents knew about oral cancer. A total of 81.7% of them were aware that smoking is a prime menacing factor associated with oral cancer, and 61.9% knew the same was true for using smokeless tobacco. Only 32.4% knew that old age was also a risk factor. A total of 56.3% of the participants correctly reported that alcohol consumption was linked with oral cancer [19].

The subject population of our study also depicted inadequate information concerning causes and factors associated with oral cancer. A total of 95.6% of our participants identified smoking as a risk factor, i.e., a greater percentage than the data from Yemen, where it was identified by 71.5% of the respondents. Smokeless tobacco use was identified by 70.9% of our respondents, which is similar to the 73.7% reported in Yemen [19]. The increased awareness of tobacco as a risk factor may be linked to anti-tobacco media campaigns highlighting the harmful effects of smoking. Unfortunately, our country has a high prevalence of tobacco use in various forms, so educating people about these adverse effects could encourage them to quit these harmful habits.

The knowledge of the respondents pertaining to the clinical presentation of oral cancer among the general public of Lahore was found to be better than that of the Yemen participants, which is remarkably unsatisfactory. Red patches were identified as early signs of oral cancer by 67.4% of the participants in Lahore, which was better than that in Yemen, where only 24.1% of the participants identified them. Only 38.8% of the Lahore respondents identified white patches as a sign of low awareness, as in the Yemen study, less than one quarter of the participants knew that the presence of white patches was an early sign of oral cancer. [20].

According to a study conducted in 2018 investigating awareness of oral cancer in Jakarta, Malaysia, only 53.2% of the public was aware of oral cancer. Compared with those in other age groups, people in the 25–45 years age group were more aware of the risk factors for ARDS [21].

A population-based study was conducted in northwestern Spain in 2021. A total of five thousand and seven hundred participants were included in the survey, of whom only 17.95% had active knowledge about oral cancer. When they were questioned about their visit to a dental examination, they recorded it once a year. These findings suggest that there are insufficient efforts to disseminate information about the early signs of oral cancer, which is why the most people lack adequate knowledge about the condition [22].

Research indicates that lack of public awareness regarding the early signs of oral cancer leads to late clinical representation, which in turn reduces survival rates. Thus, it is crucial to raise awareness and educate the public about these early signs to enable early diagnosis and treatment, as insufficient knowledge significantly impact survival outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, population of Lahore demonstrated a significant lack of awareness regarding oral cancer, particularly concerning its risk factors, signs and symptoms. This underscores the urgent need for the implementation of comprehensive educational programs aimed at recognizing these risk factors and promoting early detection of oral cancer. Such programs could effectively reach the public through mass media channels. Notably, many participants indicated that they received their information about oral cancer primarily from television, highlighting the crucial role of mass media in public education.

Limitations and recommendations:

1. Cultural beliefs and stigma were not adequately explored, creating barriers to opening dialog about oral cancer.
2. Future research should focus on in-depth interviews and focus group discussions that might yield richer insights into people's perceptions, beliefs and knowledge about oral cancer.

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REFERENCES

1. Inchingolo, F., et al. "Oral cancer: A historical review." *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17, no. 9 (2020): 3168.
2. Saadat, S., et al. "Oral cancer awareness and education within the pharmacy profession." *Journal of Oncology Pharmacy Practice* 29, no. 4 (2023): 826–832.
3. Petersen, P.E. "Oral cancer prevention and control—The approach of the World Health Organization." *Oral Oncology* 45, no. 4 (2009): 454–460.
4. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. "Oral Cancer Facts." Accessed [2024].
5. Zhang, C., et al. "The global prevalence of oral leukoplakia: a systematic review and meta-analysis from 1996 to 2022." *BMC Oral Health* 23, no. 1 (2023): 645.
6. Valero, C., et al. "Young non-smokers with oral cancer: What are we missing and why?" *Oral Oncology* 127 (2022): 105803.
7. Kulkarni, G., M. Angadi, and V. Sorganvi. "Knowledge & Attitude Regarding Oral Cancer Among College Students." *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development* 2, no. 5 (2013).
8. Warnakulasuriya, S., and A. Kerr. "Oral cancer screening: past, present, and future." *Journal of Dental Research* 100, no. 12 (2021): 1313–1320.
9. Irani, S., I. Barati, and M. Badiei. "Periodontitis and oral cancer—current concepts of the etiopathogenesis." *Oncology Reviews* 14, no. 1 (2020).
10. Petti, S. "Lifestyle risk factors for oral cancer." *Oral Oncology* 45, no. 4 (2009): 340–350.
11. Fos, P., and L. Hutchison. "The state of rural oral health: A literature review." *Rural Healthy People* (2010): 131–142.
12. Alrsheedi, M., and A. Haleem. "Knowledge, attitude and behavior of medical and dental students towards smoking habit in Saudi Arabian universities: a comparative study." *International Dental Journal Studies Research* [Internet] 1, no. 1 (2012): 1–16.
13. Kavarthapu, A., and K. Gurumoorthy. "Linking chronic periodontitis and oral cancer: A review." *Oral Oncology* 121 (2021): 105375.
14. Keser, G., G. Yilmaz, and F.N. Pekiner. "Assessment of knowledge level and awareness about human papillomavirus among dental students." *Journal of Cancer Education* 36, no. 4 (2021): 664–669.
15. Saberian, E., et al. "Oral cancer at a glance." *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Biology* 8, no. 4 (2023): 379–386.
16. Sarode, G.S., et al. "Oral cancer databases: A comprehensive review." *Journal of Oral Pathology & Medicine* 47, no. 6 (2018): 547–556.
17. Bagan, J., G. Sarrion, and Y. Jimenez. "Oral cancer: clinical features." *Oral Oncology* 46, no. 6 (2010): 414–417.
18. Gerber, H., et al. "Oral cancer awareness among patients at 3 university hospitals in Poland and Germany: A survey research." *Advances in Clinical & Experimental Medicine* 31, no. 6 (2022).
19. Al-Maweri, S.A., et al. "Oral cancer awareness of the general public in Saudi Arabia." *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention* 16 (2015): 3377–3381.
20. Macpherson, L.M. "Raising awareness of oral cancer from a public and health professional perspective." *British Dental Journal* 225, no. 9 (2018): 809–814.

21. Wimardhani, Y.S., et al. "Public awareness of oral cancer among adults in Jakarta, Indonesia." *Journal of Investigative and Clinical Dentistry* 10, no. 1 (2019): e12379.
22. Varela-Centelles, P., et al. "Oral cancer awareness in North-Western Spain: a population-based study." *Medicina Oral, Patología Oral y Cirugía Bucal* 26, no. 4 (2021): e518.
23. Dubai, S.A.R.A., et al. "Awareness and knowledge of oral cancer among university students in Malaysia." *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention* 13, no. 1 (2012): 165-168.

